

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Digital Twinning of Concrete Consolidation Quality Process

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

EU ASHVIN

DIGITAL TWINNING OF CONCRETE CONSOLIDATION QUALITY PROCESS

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

A specific model is developed by Digital Twin Technologies (DTT) and the Polytechnic University of Catalunya (UPC) for real-time monitoring of vibration quality to proactively address concrete consolidation issues.

Project Status:

Finished

Publisher:

N/A

Funded by
the European Union

Authors:

Héctor Posada (Polytechnic University of Catalunya), Rolando Chacón (Polytechnic University of Catalunya), Mary Lidiya Kennedy (Technische Universität Berlin), Eser Senturk (Technische Universität Berlin)

Introduction:

The proposed use case aims to facilitate real-time monitoring of concrete consolidation quality using digital twin data acquired from construction sites with help of accelerometers to measure the formwork accelerations during the vibration of concrete. This monitoring supports the quality control team to achieve real-time quality assurance and develop real-time solutions for concrete placement and vibration workmanship, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

The current monitoring practice relies on visual and time-consuming feedback by project managers, which can be subjective. Therefore, in the conventional method poor workmanship cannot be detected well on the spot; rather, the concrete is inspected and repaired after it becomes hardened. Hence retroactive quality control to achieve real-time quality assurance of concrete is beneficial, which can be achieved through a monitoring and warning solution for concrete placement and vibration workmanship quality, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

DTT, UPC, TUB

Partners:

Rehan Khan (Digital Twin Technologies), Héctor Posada (Polytechnic University of Catalunya), Rolando Chacón (Polytechnic University of Catalunya), Timo Hartmann (Technische Universität Berlin)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

N/A

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Digital twinning of concrete consolidation quality process Use Case
Goal	The proposed use case aims to facilitate real-time monitoring of concrete consolidation quality using accelerometer and temperature data.
Description	Real-time monitoring of vibration quality to proactively address concrete consolidation issues.
Input Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIM model with columns • Real-time sensor data.
Sequence of actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Generate BIM model with installed sensors and the scheduling data. ✓ Place thermocouples and accelerometers at strategic locations within the concrete formwork of the structural elements to collect data. ✓ Transmit the data collected by accelerometers and thermocouples to IoT-platform. ✓ Record temperature and vibration data over time generating a dataset that represents the maturity of the concrete development over time. ✓ Integrate the maturity of the concrete data with BIM model using acceleration and temperature sensors. ✓ Monitor the data and generate graphs to see evolution of concrete maturity over time and compare it with required standards. ✓ Report the issues identified and inform the asset managers. ✓ Maintain a comprehensive database of the concrete curing process which can serve as benchmark for quality control of concrete maturity.
Primary actors	QA/QC Team
Secondary actors	Construction Managers
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The BIM model including sensors and scheduling data. • Sensor measurements data from accelerometers and thermocouples.
Trigger	Assessing the quality of construction in real-time
Post-conditions	The user must assess the quality of concrete work and create relevant issues.

Frequency of use	During the casting of columns and after the casting
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	DTT, UPC, TUB
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to support real-time monitoring of concrete consolidation quality using vibration data of concrete acquired accelerometers.

In the current monitoring practice, poor workmanship cannot be detected well. However with this use case rather, high quality inspection on concrete can be achieved through a monitoring for concrete quality with sensors, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

Objectives:

The main objective of this document is to describe the methodology developed by Digital Twin Technologies (DTT), the Polytechnique University of Catalunya (UPC), and the contributing partners of ASHVIN consortium, for quality inspection of concrete consolidation using digital twin data acquired from sites. This use case is particularly useful for construction projects where the casting of similar structural elements is repetitive and continuous, enabling the assessment of concrete vibration tasks.

The current monitoring practice relies on visual and time-consuming feedback by project managers, which can be subjective. Therefore, with this conventional method poor workmanship cannot be detected well on the spot; rather, the concrete is inspected and repaired after it becomes hardened. Hence retroactive quality control to achieve real-time quality assurance of concrete is beneficial, which can be achieved through a monitoring and warning solution for concrete placement and vibration workmanship quality, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

The process models developed as part of the project, which has been validated through several demonstration projects within the EU. The referred groups for this document are construction managers, quality control teams, asset owners and business partners in the construction industry who are interested in utilising the open platform, ASHVIN, to ensure the quality of concrete consolidation during construction stage onsite.

2.3 Overall Process:

Please fill in General Description of Overall Process from the Process Map:

Figure 2 Process Map

#6 Office building in Spain (Barcelona):

The #6 demonstration project of ASHVIN are office buildings located in Barcelona (Spain) and are part of project@22 also known as 22@Barcelona and the “Innovation District” (‘Districte de la innovacio’). The objective of the 22@Barcelona project is to improve the urban, social and functional structure of the central areas alongside contributing to Barcelona’s transformation from the City of Industrial Civilization into the City of Knowledge Civilization. The project aims to convert the industrial area of Poblenou into the city’s technology and innovation district, as well as to contribute to leisure and residential spaces. Mile is an office building project of 38,093 m² divided into three complexes: MILE-Badajoz, MILE-Llul, and MILEÁvila. The access was provided for the specific module of MILE-Ávila, a cast-in-place reinforced concrete building of long-spanned post-tensioned slabs, consisting of eight levels and a total area of 16,524 m².

For the demonstration project, the objective was to assess the quality of concrete consolidation by measuring the formworks acceleration during the concrete vibration of columns. The concrete casting of the office building was continuous and sequential, as well as the accelerometer information is collected directly and concurrently along with the activity. The process of the application includes the generation of the virtual asset in the digital twin platform, the configuration of the IoT platform, the collection of data in the construction site and the end-user interaction in the digital twin platform for the assessment of consolidation quality.

The digital representation of the demonstrator is created using the BIM model of the project. Sensors are included to represent the accelerometers on the column formwork. Scheduling data for columns casting and measurement tasks are added as metadata. The implemented model represents the premises where measurements of DT data were acquired, not the whole building as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: 3D model with the sensors (accelerometers)

Regarding the IoT platform, it is necessary to create the things which represent the accelerometers, this will allow an organized storage of data in the cloud. Additionally, to enable the retrieval of sensor data within the digital twin platform, it is required to perform the BIM-IoT integration. The things created in the IoT platform, representing the sources of data (sensors and devices) must have the same Globally Unique Identifier (GUID) that the corresponding IfcSensor in the IFC-BIM model.

For taking the measurements, five accelerometers were installed on five columns between levels 4 & 5 of the buildings. Fig. 4 illustrates the floor layout plan with the encircled installed accelerometers on the column formworks. For the demo site demonstration, a high-sensitivity MEMS acceleration sensors “Kenshin-kun” were used. It is primarily a vibration monitoring system with 3 axis acceleration + temperature measurement function with high sensitivity acceleration sensor. It has a temperature operating range from -20°C to 60°C with a measurement range of $\pm 2G$.

Figure 4: Layout plan with highlighted columns with accelerometer

Fig. 5 shows the installed formwork for one of the concrete columns at the construction site. Fig. 6 shows the finished concrete columns for level 4 after the casting.

Figure 5 Concrete column formwork with installed accelerometers

Figure 6 Finished concrete columns

After the upload of the formwork accelerations measurements to the IoT platform, the data is loaded to the BIM model. Then vibration time is estimated based on the collected measures and a color scale is assigned to represent the quality of concrete consolidation work, red color indicating bad quality and green representing good quality. Results are displayed by assigning colors to the columns within the scale, allowing the quality assessment as shown in Fig. 5. A comprehensive overview of vibration tasks is provided to the construction/quality manager on the 3D model based on real-time measurements. Additionally, the use case allows for the measurements to be represented graphically with acceleration over time graphs for the highlighted columns (see Fig. 8).

Figure 7: Vibration quality based on sensed data

Figure 8: Visualization of DT data (accelerometers)

As explained above the configuration management tool integrates IoT data into the ASHVIN DT platform to allow for the seamless integration of the representation of the physical asset with IoT data collected about the behavior of the physical object itself. In summary, this demonstration of the use case allows facilitates the construction manager to carry out a quality check of the concrete consolidation work for columns.

After data processing results are computed, specific PIs are estimated to support the decisions of construction managers. Productivity of the columns casting, adequate concrete vibration, energy consumption of the equipment and percentage plan completed of related tasks are available in the digital twin platform dashboard.

PIs	Formula	Description
Vibration Time (VT)	Actual Vibration Time / Planned Vibration time	Evaluate the columns concrete consolidation
Utilization Rate (UR)	Actual Operating Time / Total Available Operating Time	Check the performance of tasks execution
Energy Efficiency (EE)	Columns Vibrated / Energy Consumption	Verify how much a project is deviating from its schedule

2.4 Disciplines:

Investigation discipline- risk assessment;

Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Construction stage

Section 3: Process-definition

Life cycle stages: Construction stage

Production information and construction

Funded by
the European Union

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

In Figure 9, exchange requirements among tools are shown. Firstly, real-time vibration and temperature data from construction sites are collected with sensors and sent to the database. BIM model of the construction site is enriched with those sensor data. The 3D representation of the building is done on parametric design software with the installed sensors also modelled on the building columns to represent the construction site. In the end, the columns in BIM model are colored according to the values. The BIM model must be generated as an open standard file to be stored on the database, providing interoperability across software, including the digital twin platform.

Figure 9: Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end

